

Establishing your credibility

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Learning designers are highly qualified learning and teaching professionals (Altena et al., 2019; Altena et al., 2025) who have struggled over the past 40 years to establish their legitimacy and credibility within universities (Szekeres, 2011). The COVID-19 pandemic and subsequent rapid pivot to online learning have assisted to some degree in the valuing and legitimatising of learning designers within universities (Petherbridge et al., 2022; Xie & Rice, 2021). At the same time, there is increasing awareness that design and teaching in universities has become increasingly complex due to the heterogeneous nature of students, changing student demands, and technological impacts on learning and teaching, particularly generative AI.

The design of learning in higher education is no longer the sole remit of the lone academic, but is a shared endeavour with specialist curriculum designers, learning designers, academic developers, learning technologists, librarians and student success coaches working in partnership with university teachers (Bawa & Watson, 2017). The positioning of learning designers as “support staff” or “techies” within institutions is unhelpful for convincing academic staff to see learning designers as equal partners (Altena et al., 2019; Prusko & Kilgore, 2023).

So, the question remains, how can learning designers and other third space workers establish their credibility within institutions?

To explore this question, an in-person workshop was held at the Third Space Symposium in Melbourne. This workshop explored the concept of credibility, which was defined as “the quality of being believable and worthy of trust” (Cambridge Dictionary, n.d.; Collins Dictionary, n.d.; Merriam-Webster Dictionary, n.d). At its core, credibility was viewed as being about human connection and understood to be multifaceted and context-specific. Credibility was conceptualised as having seven dimensions as shown in Figure 1. Importantly, it was acknowledged that credibility is not something that you can bestow upon yourself, but rather it is a gift given to us by others, which is earned through our actions and interactions with others.

Figure 1: *The seven dimensions of credibility*

Drawing upon leadership theory and positive psychology, the workshop took a proactive, strengths-based approach where upward spiral conversations were encouraged, and the tall poppy syndrome and imposter syndrome were discouraged. The message to participants was:

*“We can’t get others to believe us
if we don’t believe ourselves.” (Jolles, 2018)*

Three learning designers shared their 30 practical strategies they use for building their credibility and profiles within and outside of their institutions. Some examples included:

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Make effective use of your email signature to show your title, qualifications, awards received and publications.

Build your professional profile and promote your work on social media (see "What's Beyond Twitter / X?" in these proceedings).

Prior to meeting with an academic, send a short, friendly email introduction that includes examples of your previous work.

Participants were subsequently encouraged to share and discuss their own strategies for building their credibility with others in the room. In the second part of the workshop, participants had the opportunity to use the My Credibility Map and Action Plan as shown in Figure 2, to identify who and why they need or want to develop credibility with, and to then prepare an action plan with dates about the proactive steps they could take towards building or further strengthening their credibility.

Figure 2: My credibility and action plan canvas

My Credibility Map and Action Plan

NEED	Who I need credibility with 	Why? 	What? 	When?
	Who I want credibility with 	Why? 	What? 	When?

Workshop participants were then encouraged to complete a 1-week, 4-month and 12-month commitment card (Figure 3) and seal each commitment card in an envelope to be taken with them back to their workplace. Participants were invited to add their name to an email list indicating that they would like reminder emails sent inviting them to open their commitment envelopes over the course of the next year. Throughout 2024–2025 those who registered have received reminder emails from the facilitators one week, four months and 12 months after the workshop to prompt them to open their envelope and to check-in and act if they have not committed to their identified action.

Figure 3: Example of a My Credibility commitment card

Reflection

Our aim in preparing this workshop for the Third Space Symposium was to give back to the community who had so generously assisted us by being willing to complete a survey or be interviewed by us for our research into the profession.

In preparing for this workshop, we found that it provided us with the unexpected benefit of reflecting on how each of us in our roles have developed our credibility within our institutions and to examine the similarities and differences in our approaches.

Through our workshop we gave our third space colleagues the gift of time to stop ... think ... and reflect on their own credibility and why it is important for them. Purposefully designing the workshop to involve participants in individual, quiet time for reflection activities and collaborative discussions provided a beautiful ebb and flow to the workshop for both the introverts and extraverts in the group. The buzz in the room, the rich conversations, sharing of ideas and connections that were made was more than we had dared to dream and was inspiring for us as the workshop facilitators. It highlighted the value in bringing third space professionals from different institutions together in the one physical space to share their experiences, expertise and the challenges we face individually as we try to establish ourselves as part of a recognised profession in our institutions.

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